

THE USE OF SOME THIOLYCOLLANILIDES IN INORGANIC ANALYSIS. PART II

R. C. SWAIN, R. N. MISRA AND S. S. GUHA SIRCAR

The use of 9 thioglycollanilides in inorganic analysis has been studied. Precipitates or colour changes were produced with Ag, Pb, Hg⁺, Hg²⁺, Cu, Cd, Bi, Sn, Zn, Co, Ni and molybdate in most cases. Sensitivity limits for cobalt were found to be 0.5 to 0.25γ with the reagents. Gravimetric estimations of silver with 4 reagents and of cobalt with 3 reagents have been described.

The use of ten new thioglycollanilides in inorganic analysis has been discussed in an earlier paper (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 127). Some more thioglycollanilides, derived from simpler aromatic amines, have now been studied from the same point of view, and form the subject matter of the present communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The compounds were prepared by direct condensation of thioglycollic acid and an aromatic amine in an atmosphere of CO₂, at 110°-120°, by the improved method described earlier in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The amines used were *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines, *p*-aminobenzoic acid, *o*- and *m*-anisidines, *p*-nitroaniline and α -naphthylamine. Excepting the toluidine derivatives, which were known previously (Heilbron and Bunbury, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', 1943, Vol. III, p. 752), the others are new. The melting points, % sulphur and some physical properties of the compounds are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

[M = -(CO.CH₂.SH). sol. = soluble. sp. = sparingly]

Serial No.	Compounds.	M.P.	% Sulphur.		Properties.
			Found.	Calc.	
1.	<i>m</i> -M-toluene	150°	17.54	17.68	White, odourless crystal; insol. in water & dil. HCl; sol. in alcohol or acetone.
2.	<i>p</i> -M-toluene	125°	17.35	17.68	Do; do
3.	<i>m</i> -M-chlorobenzene	75°	15.92	15.87	Do; do, with disagreeable odour.
4.	<i>p</i> -M-chlorobenzene	26°	16.27	15.87	Do; do, almost odourless.
5.	<i>p</i> -M-benzoic acid	221°	15.44	15.17	Do; do, & readily sol. in cold dil. alkalis; liberates CO ₂ of NaHCO ₃ solution.
6.	<i>o</i> -M-anisole	65-66°	16.73	16.24	White, odourless crystal; insol. in water or dil. HCl, highly sol. in alcohol or acetone.
7.	<i>p</i> -M-anisole	115°	16.15	16.24	White odourless crystal; insol. in water or dil. HCl; highly sol. in alcohol or acetone.
8.	<i>p</i> -M-nitrobenzene	181°	15.57	15.10	Pale yellow; do do
9.	α -M-naphthalene	180°	15.13	14.74	White powder; insol. in water, or dil. HCl, but sol. in alcohol & acetone.

Use in Qualitative Analysis

Molar solutions of a soluble salt of Ag, Pb, Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd, Bi, As, Sb, Sn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al, Cr, Mn, Zn, Co, Ni, Ca, Sr, Ba, Mg, MoO₄²⁻ and WO₄²⁻ were used in the tests. The tests were carried out at different p_H ranges, for which use was made of a series of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffers with p_H 3.42, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0. Tests in neutral solutions were regarded as being carried out at p_H 7. For reactions at higher p_H , ammoniacal solutions of cations, where possible, were used. Same procedure, as described in Part I, was employed for making the tests (*loc. cit.*). The results of the investigation are summarised below.

The *m*-toluidine derivative, at p_H 3.42-7.0, gave light yellow precipitates with Ag and Pb, grey with Hg^I, white with Hg^{II} and Cd, pink with Co and at p_H 5-7, a brown precipitate with Ni. The Co and Ni complexes were voluminous precipitates in ammoniacal medium. Molybdate gave a yellow precipitate at p_H 3.42, but the solution turned blue on keeping or heating; at p_H 4-7 the solution turned blue gradually on keeping. All the precipitates, excepting the molybdate complex, were insoluble in dilute alcohol, but the latter was soluble affording a blue solution on heating. The Ag and Hg^I complexes were insoluble in dilute acids. The cobalt complex was stable even in cold concentrated acids. Complete precipitation was noted in case of Ag, Hg^{II}, and in ammoniacal solution, of Co.

The *p*-toluidine derivative, at p_H 3.42-7, yielded pale yellow precipitates with Ag and Pb, grey with Hg^I, white with Hg^{II}, pink with Co, and at p_H 5-7 brown precipitate with Ni. Molybdate behaved similarly to the above reagent. In ammoniacal medium the Co and Ni complexes were voluminous. The nature of the complexes was almost the same as in the case of the above reagent. Complexes of Ag, Hg^{II}, and in ammoniacal medium, Co appeared quantitative.

The *m*-chloroaniline derivative, at p_H 3.42-7, furnished yellow precipitates with Ag, Pb, Cu and Bi; grey with Hg^I; white with Hg^{II} and Cd; pink with Co, and at p_H 5-7 a brown precipitate with Ni. Molybdate behaved as with the above reagents. In ammoniacal medium Co and Ni complexes were voluminous. The silver complex was insoluble in dilute alcohol, dilute HNO₃ and NH₄OH, and did not decompose in boiling water; the complex was soluble in HNO₃ (conc.). The Pb, Hg^I, Hg^{II}, Cd, Co and Ni complexes were similar to those of the above reagents. The Bi-complex was partially soluble in hot alcohol and insoluble in cold dilute acids. The Cu-complex was yellowish brown at p_H 4-6; it was not stable; it was partly soluble in alcohol and in hot dilute HCl; in ammoniacal solution a black precipitate, probably of the sulphide, was obtained. Complete precipitation took place in case of Ag, and in ammoniacal medium, of Co.

The *p*-chloroaniline compound, at p_H 3.42-7, gave yellow precipitates with Ag, Pb, and Bi (at p_H 5-6); grey with Hg^I; white with Hg^{II} and Cd (at p_H 5-6); pink with Co and brown with Ni (p_H 5-7). Molybdate behaved similarly to the above reagents. In ammoniacal medium Co and Ni gave voluminous precipitates. The nature of the complexes were the same as in case of the above reagent.

The PABA derivative, at p_H 3.42-7, gave yellow precipitates with Ag and Bi; grey with Hg^I; white with Hg^{II}, Cd, Sb, Sn and Zn (at p_H 4-6); greyish brown with Cu,

yellowish grey with Fe^{III} , pink precipitate and colour with Co (p_n 4-6), and brown with Ni (p_n 4-6). In ammoniacal medium Co and Ni produced deep blood-red and brown coloration respectively; on long standing or on heating partial precipitation of the Co-complex in blood-red colour took place, and the gradually developed Ni-coloration faded slowly. At p_n 3.42 molybdate produced a yellow coloration which on standing gave yellow precipitate; at p_n 4, faint yellow coloration followed by precipitation occurred; and at these and at p_n 5, 6, 7, blue coloration gradually developed on long standing. The yellow molybdate precipitate on heating or standing turned the solution first green and then blue; the precipitate was almost insoluble in alcohol. The silver complex turned white on heating. Solubilities of the Ag, Pb, Hg^{I} , Hg^{II} and Bi complexes were similar to the corresponding complexes of the above reagent. The Cu, Cd, Sb, Sn, Fe^{III} and Zn complexes were insoluble in dilute alcohol, but soluble in dilute HCl or HNO_3 . The Co and Ni colorations could not be extracted with ether, benzene or amyl alcohol. Complete precipitation took place in case of Ag, Hg^{II} , Cd and Zn (p_n 6).

The *o*-anisidine compound, at p_n 3.42-7, gave yellow precipitates with Ag, Pb and Bi; grey with Hg^{I} ; white with Hg^{II} and Cd; yellowish grey with Cu; pink with Co, and at p_n 4-6, brown with Ni. Molybdate exhibited yellow-blue colour change. In ammoniacal solution Co and Ni gave voluminous precipitates. The Pb and Cu complexes were soluble in hot alcohol. The Ag-complex was not decomposed at the temperature of boiling water and melted with decomposition at 222° . Solubilities of the Ag, Hg^{I} , Hg^{II} , Cd and Bi complexes were the same as the corresponding complexes of the above reagent. The Ni-complex was partly soluble in alcohol and completely in dilute HNO_3 or H_2SO_4 . But the Co-complex was resistant to cold HCl (conc.) or HNO_3 . The complexes of Ag, Hg^{II} and Co (in ammoniacal solution) were completely precipitated.

The *p*-anisidine derivative, at p_n 3.42-7, gave yellow precipitates with Ag, Pb and Bi; grey with Hg^{I} ; white with Hg^{II} ; pink with Co and brown with Ni (p_n 4-6). Molybdate behaved similarly as in the above case. In ammoniacal medium Co and Ni complexes were voluminous. The nature of the complexes was the same as in case of the corresponding complexes of the above reagent, but the Pb complex was almost insoluble in dilute alcohol.

The derivative of *p*-nitroaniline, at p_n 3.42-7, produced yellow precipitate with Ag and Pb; grey with Hg^{I} ; white with Hg^{II} , Cd and Bi; light brown with Co; brown with Ni (p_n 5-7), and yellow precipitate with MoO_4 (p_n 3.42 1), turning blue on heating or keeping. In ammoniacal medium Co and Ni complexes were voluminous. The silver complex turned brown on heating. Complexes of Ag, Pb, Hg^{I} , Hg^{II} , Cu, Cd, Bi, Co and Ni were insoluble in dilute alcohol; complexes of Ag and Hg^{I} were insoluble in dilute mineral acids, and the cobalt complex was fairly insoluble in concentrated HCl or HNO_3 . Complexes of Ag, Hg^{II} and Co (in ammoniacal solution) were quantitative.

The α -naphthylamine derivative, at p_n 3.42-7, gave yellow precipitates with Ag and Pb; grey with Hg^{I} , white with Hg^{II} and Cd; pink with Co; brown with Ni (p_n 5-7), and yellow-blue colour change with MoO_4 . The complexes were insoluble in alcohol. The Ag and Hg^{I} complexes were insoluble in dilute mineral acids, and the

cobalt complex was insoluble even in concentrated HCl or HNO₃. The Ag-complex turned brown on heating. Complete precipitation of Ag and Co (in ammoniacal solution) was noted:

Sensitivity Tests

Sensitivity tests for cobalt with the thioglycollanilides were carried out as the pink colour of the complexes was very dark. Ammoniacal solution was chosen as the test medium, since the complexes were voluminosely precipitated from such medium. Solutions of CoCl₂·2H₂O (E. Merck, analytical grade) were prepared in the ammoniacal test medium (a solution containing 2% NH₄Cl and 2N-NH₄OH), the concentrations of cobalt being, 1:10³, 1:10⁴, 1:10⁵, 1:10^{5.5}, 1:10⁶, 1:10^{6.5}, 1:10⁷, 1:10⁸, 1:10^{8.5}, 1:10⁹ respectively; 1 c.c. each from these solutions was treated with 2 drops of a freshly prepared 1% solution of the reagent. The resulting colour changes and precipitations were noted in cold and on warming. In some cases the coloration produced was found to be adsorbed on the reagent that usually came down due to dilution of the alcoholic solution. Almost in all cases the precipitation limit fell between cobalt concentration 1:10³ and 1:10⁴. Table II records the limiting concentrations for identification of cobalt with the respective reagents. The limit of identification (in γ) has been obtained from filter paper spot test, in which a drop of cobalt solution of definite concentration was added to a filter paper; the paper was dried, a drop of the reagent solution was added over the spot, and the paper was held over the mouth of a bottle of ammonia.

TABLE II

Sl. No. of reagents ...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Limiting conc. =10 ^{-x} , where x=	6.0	5.7	6.3	5.7	5.0	5.3	5.3	5.6	5.0
Identification limits (in γ)	... 0.05	0.25	0.05	0.25	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.25	0.50

Use in the Gravimetric Analysis

Some of the thioglycollanilides were used in gravimetric estimations of Ag and Co, since qualitative analysis indicated complete removal of these cations from their solutions by the reagents.

Silver Complexes.—Silver formed yellow complexes with the thioglycollanilides, which were, in general, precipitated completely from a solution of AgNO₃ in slightly acidic medium. Some of these complexes were not decomposed when heated on a water-bath, and attempt was made to ascertain their applicability in silver estimation. The reagents used were *o*-(mercaptoacetamido)-anisole, *m*- and *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-chlorobenzenes and *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-toluene.

The complexes were precipitated by addition of an 1% alcoholic solution of the respective reagent to a hot AgNO₃ solution, the mixture being digested on a water-bath for about half to one hour, filtered, washed free from excess of the reagent by hot dilute alcohol, and dried at 100°-110°. A known weight of the dried complex

was then ignited in a porcelain crucible and weighed as metallic silver. From this the %Ag in the complexes was calculated. Table III records the %silver and the assumed composition of the complexes.

TABLE III

(% Ag found is the mean of 3 expts.)

Sl. No. of reagent.	Assumed composition.	Found.	% Silver.	Calc.
2.	[(p) $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.CO.CH}_2\text{S}$] Ag, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	33.92		33.31
3.	[(m) $\text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.CO.CH}_2\text{S}$] Ag	34.90		34.78
4.	[(p) $\text{Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.CO.CH}_2\text{S}$] Ag	34.88		34.78
6.	[(o) $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.CO.CH}_2\text{S}$] Ag	35.40		35.49

In gravimetric determination of the metal by direct weighing of the complexes the above assumed compositions were taken into account.

For estimation, 10 c.c. of a standard $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$ solution was pipetted out, diluted to 100 c.c., acidified with 4 drops of HNO_3 (conc.), and was heated to gentle boiling. To this hot solution a freshly prepared 1% alcoholic solution of the organic reagent was added from a pipette slowly with constant stirring till precipitation appeared to be complete. In case of the methoxy compound, under the above conditions the precipitate began to coagulate as the equivalence point approached. The precipitate was digested on a water-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour when complete coagulation took place. Complete precipitation was ensured by addition of a further small amount of the precipitant, and digestion was continued for about one hour more. The content was cooled and allowed to stand at room temperature for several minutes. The precipitate was filtered through a weighed G₄-crucible, washed free from excess of the reagent by hot water in all the cases, and finally dried at $100^\circ\text{--}110^\circ$ to a constant weight. The results of estimations are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Ag taken = 0.1082 g. Drying temp. = $100^\circ\text{--}110^\circ$.

Wt. of complexes.	Ag found.						
Reagent No.2.		Reagent No.3.		Reagent No.4.		Reagent No.6.	
0.3198 g.	0.1065 g.	0.3076 g.	0.1076 g.	0.3106 g.	0.1080 g.	0.3066 g.	0.1088 g.
0.3208	0.1069	0.3078	0.1076	0.3106	0.1080	0.3056	0.1085
0.3198	0.1065	0.3072	0.1074	0.3100	0.1079	0.3060	0.1086
0.3204	0.1067						

Cobalt Complexes.—The thioglycollanilides form dark pink complexes with cobalt which are voluminously precipitated from a faintly ammoniacal solution. It has been shown earlier that these are cobaltic complexes (*loc. cit.*), and the same procedure for estimation of cobalt has been employed in the present investigation.

The reagents used were *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-chlorobenzene, *o*-(mercaptoacetamido)-anisole and *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-toluene. The former two reagents provided fairly reproducible results when the complexes were directly weighed as such, but the latter afforded variable results in such methods. The chloro compound gave 0.3503 g. of complex at 110° drying temperature (mean of 3 experiments) from 10 c.c. of the solution, indicating the amount of cobalt to be 0.03125 g. against 0.03163 g. The methoxy compound gave 0.3434 g. complex at 100°, indicating 0.03126 g. of Co against 0.03163 g. from the same solution. The composition of the complexes assumed in the above calculation corresponds to the cobaltic complexes having no associated water molecules. The complex obtained in case of the *p*-(mercaptoacetamido)-toluene from 10 c.c. of the standard solution was filtered through an ashless (Whatman No. 42) filter paper, washed several times with warm water till free of chloride (since NH_4Cl was added to the solution in the precipitation process), dried, ignited to Co_2O_3 in a porcelain crucible, and hence, the amount of cobalt was calculated. By this process cobalt found was 0.03158 g. against 0.03163 g.

Thanks are due to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, Govt of India, for supporting this research with an award of a junior research scholarship to one of the authors (R.N.M.).

MAVURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK-3.

Received March 19, 1955.